

Micro-Finance as A Tool for Financial Inclusion

Dr. Ramdas Nagoji Bolake

Assistant Professor and Head, Department of Commerce, Kankavli College Kankavli

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Abstract:

Microfinance has assumed immense importance throughout the world in view of its efficiency in credit dispensation, loan repayment and reduction of poverty. The experience world over has proved that hassle free and repetitive dose of credit is the basic need of the poor which has become the hallmark of microfinance. Several countries like Bangladesh, Indonesia, Philippines, Kenya and Bolivia have implemented microfinance programmes with encouraging results. In the Indian context, the microfinance sector has witnessed an unprecedented growth in the last few years, and has firmly established itself as significant potential contributor in the government's agenda of "Financial Inclusion". Financial services for the poor have proved to be a powerful instrument for poverty reduction that enables the poor to build assets, increase incomes, and reduce their vulnerability to economic stress. Financial inclusion, we mean the delivery of financial services, including banking services and credit, at an affordable cost to the vast sections of disadvantaged and low-income groups who tend to be excluded. The various financial services include access to savings, loans, insurance, payments and remittance facilities offered by the formal financial system.

Keywords: Micro- Finance, Financial Services, Productive Loans

Introduction:

In the Indian context, the microfinance sector has witnessed an unprecedented growth in the last few years, and has firmly established itself as significant potential contributor in the government's agenda of "Financial Inclusion". Financial services for the poor have proved to be a powerful instrument for poverty reduction that enables the poor to build assets, increase incomes, and reduce their vulnerability to economic stress. Microfinance aims at providing broad range of financial services such as deposits, Loans, payment services, money transfers, insurance to poor and low-income households and their micro enterprises. The objective of 100 per cent financial inclusion cannot be achieved by the Government of India unless it looks for its enforcement in each and every part of the country. The main focus is required in the rural and remote areas. One of the most significant factors which budget towards the financial inclusion of the rural and remote population is the microfinance services. In fact, microfinance is the

only way through which the financial inclusion can penetrate into the rural and remote areas which expose the most under developed territory of the country. In this paper, we have mainly focused upon the achievements of the microfinance services towards financial inclusion.

The paper highlights the roadblocks of micro finance in India. It looks into the attempts of selected organisations in the field of micro finance in India. The paper presents a glance into the government's efforts in the field of micro finance. Micro finance serves as an umbrella term that describes the provision of banking services by poverty focused micro finance institutions to poor parts of the population that are not being served by mainstream financial services providers.

1. Micro Finance – An Overview:

Micro finance refers to the provision of financial services to poor or low income clients, including consumers and the self-employed. The term also refers to the practice of sustainably delivering those services. More broadly, it refers to

a movement that envisions “a world in which as many poor and near poor households as possible have permanent access to an appropriate range of high quality financial services, including not just credit but also savings, insurance and fund transfers. Micro finance can be defined as small loans that help poor people who wish to start or expand their small businesses but are not able to get banks to lend to them. Micro credit is the extension of small loans to entrepreneurs too poor to qualify for traditional bank loans. It is helping millions of poor people, especially poor rural women; with tiny loans so they can start small, create self employment and improve their lives. Microfinance is the supply of loans, savings, and other basic financial services to the poor. People living in poverty, like everyone else, need a diverse range of financial instruments to run their businesses, build assets, stabilize consumption, and should themselves against risks. Financial services needed by the poor include working capital loans, consumer credit and savings, pensions, insurance and money transfer services. Microfinance aims at providing broad range of financial services such as deposits, Loans, payment services, money transfers, insurance to poor and low-income households and their micro enterprises.

Review Of Literature:

One of the key assumptions of microfinance programmes is that it can help the poor, especially, to develop new income generating activities (IGA) or at least strengthen existing IGA. Available empirical studies give controversial results. While some studies give positive results of earlier studies **Kevane and Wydick, (2001)**, In his research paper examine that emphasize the very limited effects in terms of IGA and some time the drawbacks of microfinance: loans mainly used for “non productive purpose” or appropriated by males, women confined into the least profitable sectors, market saturation and displacement effects, etc.

Kalpana et. al (2002) In his paper this study In-depth analyses report a diversity of women profiles and therefore a diversity of effects and results.

Fernandez and Karmakar, (2008) advocate that microcredit for entrepreneurship is only possible beyond the ‘minimalist approach’ of mere financial intervention. They are of the opinion that credit for enterprise development is important but can be achieved only with the provision of support services preferable by other development promoters

Nair’s (2005) study on attitudes to income generation and work among fishermen. She discusses here how the introduction of microcredit financed fishing nets, “increased the productivity of fishing activity technically” but “the average income and consumption levels of many of the households” did not increase “to any significant extent”. She explains how this is linked to many fishermen cutting down on the number of fishing days. This means planning is not just done at the policy level but also at the beneficiary level where local social dynamics play a key role.

What Is Financial Inclusion?

There are many different definition of financial inclusion. Financial inclusion or inclusive growth is the availability of banking services at an affordable cost to disadvantaged and low-income groups. Opposite of financial inclusion is financial exclusion. A group or person which can be consider as financially excluded if they do not have access to formal financial services such as banking facility.

By financial inclusion, we mean the delivery of financial services, including banking services and credit, at an affordable cost to the vast sections of disadvantaged and low-income groups who tend to be excluded. The various financial services include access to savings, loans, insurance, payments and remittance facilities offered by the formal financial system. Among the key services that are of great relevance here are risk management or risk mitigation services vis-à-vis economic shocks. Such shocks may be an income shock due to adverse weather conditions or natural disasters, or an expenditure shock due to health emergencies or accidents, leading to a high level of unexpected expenditure. This aspect of financial inclusion is of

vital importance in providing economic security to individuals and families.

Objectives Of The Study:

The objective of the present study is as follows:

1. To Study the role of Micro-finance in Poverty Reduction in India
2. To examine the Roadblocks For Micro Finance
3. To Study the models micro finance under financial inclusion.

Research Methodology:

Secondary sources of data are used. Data published by various institutions such as Government of India, World Bank, Reserve Bank of India (RBI), National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD, State Level Bankers" Committee (SLBC), etc are used for the purpose of the present paper.

Role Of Micro-Finance In Poverty Reduction:

Microfinance is about providing financial services to the poor who are not served by the conventional formal financial institutions - it is about extending the frontiers of financial service provision. The provision of such financial services requires innovative delivery channels and methodologies. The needs for financial services that allow people to both take advantage of opportunities and better management of their resources. Microfinance can be one effective tool amongst many for poverty alleviation. However, it should be used with caution-despite recent claims, the equation between microfinance and poverty alleviation is not straight-forward, because poverty is a complex phenomenon and many constraints that the poor in general have to cope with. We need to understand when and in what form microfinance is appropriate for the poorest; the delivery channel, methodology and products offered are all inter-linked and in turn affect the prospect and promise of poverty alleviation. Access to formal banking

services is difficult for the poor. The main problem the poor have to take when trying to acquire loans from formal financial institutions is the demand for collateral asked by these institutions. In addition, the process of acquiring a loan entails many bureaucratic procedures, which lead to extra transaction costs for the poor. Formal financial institutions are not motivated to lend money to them. In general, formal financial institutions show a preference for urban over rural sectors, large-scale over small scale transactions, and non-agricultural over agricultural loans. Formal financial institutions have little incentives to lend to the rural poor for the following reasons.

1. **Administrable difficulties:** Small rural farmers often live geographically scattered, in areas with poor communication facilities, making loan administration difficult.
2. **Systematic risks:** Agricultural production is associated with some systemic risks, such as drought and floods, which is reflected in a high covariance of local incomes.
3. **Lack of information:** The absence of standardized information, Standard lending tools, such as financial statements or credit histories, does not exist in these areas.
4. **Repayment problems:** The repayment of working capital may be required only once a year for example during the harvest season. On the other hand, access to informal loans is relatively easy, convenient, and available locally to low income households for the following reasons:-
 - Informal moneylenders use interlinked credit contracts to reduce default risk such as development of business relationship with the clients.
 - Informal moneylenders have local information which helps them to appraise credit needs and credit worthiness of the client.
 - Informal moneylenders are considering the needs and requirements of clients even for small amount of loan.

- Informal money lenders will profit from social sanctions such as those that may exist among members of a family. These sanctions may serve as a substitute for legal enforcement.
- Informal money lenders use specific incentives to stimulate repayment, such as repeat lending to borrowers who repay promptly, with gradually increasing loan size. Despite the fact that many rural poor acquire their loans from the informal financial sector in rural areas of developing countries; the sector has some basic limitations.
- A common feature of many rural communities is that much of the local information does not flow freely; it tends to be segmented and circulates only within specific groups. Usually the informal credit market is based on local economies and is thus limited by local wealth constraints and the covariant risks of the local environment. Since most of the world's poor do not have access to basic financial services that would help them manage their assets and generate income.
- To overcome poverty, they need to be able to borrow, save, and invest, and to protect their families against adversity. Another shortcoming of the two financial sectors in developing countries is their inability to satisfy the credit needs of the poor that has led to the new development of micro finance.
- Micro finance is believed to be able to reduce the above-mentioned inadequacies of formal and informal financial institutions and is emerging as an important credit partner to the poor in the developing world.

2. Models Of Micro Finance:

There are two models of micro-finance which are prevalent in India:

Direct Financing Model:

In this model (also known as Micro Finance Institution Model) the bank lends money to an

NGO. The NGO promotes and imparts training to the Self Help Groups and also gives credit to them.

Self Help Group Bank Linkage Model:

In this model SHGs act as a bridge between bankers and the grass root clients. Banks transfer funds to micro finance bodies that are responsible for disbursal and collection. The intermediation cost could be around 6% of the loan amount. The risk completely lies with the banks - the advances to the SHGs would be reflected in the portfolios of the banks. Banks do not mind taking the risk as servicing the grass-root level customers who are illiterate would otherwise involve a lot of transaction costs. A majority of these grass-root level customers have no means to produce ration card, identity card and even filling up application forms, which are the bare requirements to obtain loans in the normal course of bank lending operations. NABARD oversees the linking programme of banks to SHGs and offers refinance for it whereas SIDBI, through the SIDBI foundation for micro credit (SFMC) lends to Micro Finance Institutions. The Self-Help Group-Bank Linkage Programme implemented by commercial banks, Regional Rural Banks and Co-operative banks has emerged as a major micro finance programme in India, with 1.6 million SHGs being linked to banks in 2014-15 with the total flow of credit to them of over Rs. 6,800 crores.

Objectives Of Micro Finance:

The objectives of micro finance can be highlighted herein below:

1. It provides a model of development that is Bottom up;
2. It promotes entrepreneurship and gives people the means to brawl poverty;
3. Micro-finance can be a powerful device in initiating a cyclical process of growth and development;
4. Micro-finance activity can improve the access of rural poor to financial services;
5. The micro-finance interventions help in inculcating necessary habits for economic

independence and self-reliance. Appropriate and participatory credit plans by the members of a group can help in social and economic empowerment;

6. Increased access signifies the overcoming of isolation of rural women in terms of their access to financial services and denial of credit due to absence of collateral security;
7. The collection of savings generated out of very small but regular voluntary contributions improves access of the poor women to bank loans;
8. It could also help in strengthening poor families' resistance to external shocks and reducing dependence on moneylenders;
9. The group utilizes its corpus to disburse loans of small amount amongst the needy members. In the beginning, the members meet out their consumption needs out of their own fund and afterwards they obtain loans from the Banks for taking up some economic activities for their sustained living.

Road Blocks For Micro Finance:

As part of this growth stage, microfinance in India is undergoing rapid changes and discovering new challenges. Collecting money from scattered, remote clients, the cost of service delivery transactions in the "last mile", effective information exchange at the institutional level, and effective growth management are just a few of the many challenges confronting MFIs.

1. Time Consuming: Generally a borrower repaid the loan weekly and so for an annual loan of Rs 5000, a collection officer had to visit 52 times, pushing up the transaction cost per loan.

2. Regulatory Hurdles: The microfinance industry faces huge regulatory hurdles in raising finances. It has limited access to foreign capital, either as equity or even as borrowings. It has to rely largely on bank financing (loans to MFIs, fortunately, qualify for priority sector lending). This has other associated cost-related problems. Most microfinance companies in the country today borrow at 11%-12%

from banks. Transaction costs add another 10%-11%. Add another 2% as normal margin, cushion for debt defaults and capital adequacy and the rate works out to 23%-24%.

3. Non-Productive Loans And Procedural Delays For Productive Loans: Since most of the poor and needy are illiterate and prefer loans for consumption rather than productive purposes, majority of the poor find it hard to get loans sanctioned for taking up economic activities, even if they want to. Sometimes, the loan less are asked to furnish some documents and collateral security against the loan sanctioned, contrary to the directives of the Government and the RBI.

4. Financial Viability: MFIs operating on small-scale face financial problems. Meeting administrative overheads and generating surpluses for expansion out of the spread between their interest income and the interest they pay on the bank finance may become difficult. The average borrowing costs of MFIs have increased from 10.5% in 2001-02 to 12% in 2004-05. High borrowing costs coupled with high operating expenses ranging between 4 to 19 per cent impede MFIs ability to offer competitive rates to the customer-beneficiaries. As against this, public sector banks lend directly to SHGs at interest rates varying between 9 to 12 per cent.

5. Capacity Building of the SHGs: Training and strengthening the groups, improving their accounting, increasing their monthly savings to enable them to avail of larger loans in successive rounds of borrowing, providing marketing facilities and infrastructural facilities to the products that they manufacture are huge challenges before the MFIs.

6. Inflexibility and Delay: The rigid systems and procedures for sanctioning loans and disbursing them to the beneficiaries result in a lot of delay in time for the borrowers, which de-motivate them.

7. High Interest Rates: Comparatively higher interest rate (12-36 per cent per annum) charged by the MFIs has again become a contentious issue. Sometimes, a few financial institutions charge the beneficiaries of a group high interest rate which

makes the repayment difficult for the very poor. The poorest of the poor are, therefore, unable to access the micro-finance benefits. The high interest rate collected by the MFIs from their poor clients is still perceived as exploitative in some quarters. Rate of interest has to be reduced

8. High Transaction Costs: Although the interest rate offered to the borrowers is regulated, the transaction costs in terms of the number of trips to be made, the documents to be furnished etc. plus the illegal charges demanded by the lending institutions clandestinely, result in increasing the cost of borrowing, thus, making it less attractive to the borrowers.

9. Lack of Trained Staff: One of the biggest challenges in urban micro-finance may well be recruiting people with the right service orientation. The salesmen need to be able to relate to the people they lend to and not be seen as condescending. The typical urban salesman who likes to be seen with the latest cell phone model definitely does not fit into this mould.

10. Social Obligation, Not a Business Opportunity: Micro-finance has been seen as a

social obligation rather than a potential business opportunity.

11. Capital Funds: MFIs growth is constrained by the capacity of their staff and the availability of capital funds. Indian MFIs are depending on donor funds

12. Lack of Training: In most of the cases, it has been found that members of a group take up certain economic activities for their sustenance which are not preceded by relevant training. After the pioneering efforts of the last few years by the government banks, NGOs, and so on, the micro-finance scene is reaching the take-off point.

13. Rural Financial Inclusion: Some details pertaining to the progress made by the banking sector in enhancing financial inclusion in rural areas are available in the Reserve Bank's Report on Trend and Progress of Banking in India: 2010-11. The progress made so far is not very impressive, when compared to the extent of financial exclusion which continues to exist. A few indicators of the progress made in this area are furnished in Table-1.

Table: 1: Progress Made in Financial Inclusion in the Rural Sector

Indicators	2009	2010	2021
Total Villages Covered	54,757 99,840	Villages Covered - with population >2000 27,743 53,397	Villages Covered - with population <2000 27,014 46,443
Villages covered through Branches	21,499 22,684	Villages covered through Business 33,158 76,801	Correspondents
Villages covered through other modes	100 355	(Mobile van and ATM)	Kisan Credit Cards (million) 20 23
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Source: Reports on Trend and Progress on Banking in India, 2020-21

Roles And Activities:

Discussion / Awareness programme on (A)
General Banking and their advantage

1. **Deposits:** Importance of saving/deposit, opening of account, KYC norms, nomination facilities, type of accounts, available/applicable rate of interest, mode of withdrawal/credit, customers right & obligations towards bank, fair practice etc.
2. **Credit:** Availability of different forms of Credit for various activities and assistance available from different Govt. agencies for self and employment generation through various Central & State Govt. sponsored scheme / programmes such as SGSY, SGRY, PMEGP, IAY, BSKP, SCP, FFDA, USKP, NRLM etc.
3. **Agriculture:** Important information relating to cropping pattern, scale of finance, proper marketing of produce, storage, Govt. Priorities and programmes for Agriculture growth.
4. **Availability of different assistance from agencies** like NABARD, NHB, CGTMSE, RSETI, DRDC, DIC, NAIS etc.
5. **Formation of SHG, JLG, Farmers club** and benefits there on, Agri clinics/Agribusiness and other women and child development schemes.
6. **Support from various Govt. institutions / agencies** by way of subsidy, grant reimbursement etc.
7. **Importance of interest subvention** announced by Central & State Govt and its availability under various schemes.
7. **Insurance:** Various products of insurance in Life & Non-Life offered by Govt. and Insurance Companies beneficial to the people of the area.

8. **Financial Inclusion:** Awareness about the seriousness and importance being given by the Govt. to cover all the villages and families under the purview of banking and benefits to rural / urban people and awareness on various activities and products coming under financial inclusion plan.

9. **Restructuring:** To make aware to distressed borrower about the recourse available for resolving unmanageable debt portfolio arises out of natural calamities/unforeseen circumstances beyond the control of borrower with effective debt restructuring plans in-consultation with bank branch.

10. **Coverage:** While credit counselling services may be provided in rural, semi urban, urban and metropolitan areas, banks may adopt a segmented approach specific to different categories of borrowers, rather than broad-based generalized one.

Conclusion:

Finance is the lubricant, which oils the wheels of development. All economies rely upon the intermediary function of finance to transfer resources from savers to investors. The process of financial inclusion is an attempt to bring within the ambit of the organized financial system the weaker and vulnerable sections of society. Financial inclusion can be defined as the delivery of credit and other financial service at an affordable cost to the vast sections of the disadvantaged and low income groups. The objective of financial inclusion is to extend the scope of activities of the organized financial system to include, within its ambit, people with low incomes. Accessing small amounts of credit at reasonable interest rates give poor people an opportunity to set up their own small business.

Many studies show that poor people are trustable, with higher repayment rates than conventional borrowers. When poor people have access to financial services, they can earn more, build their assets, and cushion themselves against

external shocks. Poor households use microfinance to move from everyday survival to planning for the future: they invest in better nutrition, housing, health, and education. Most poor people cannot get good financial services that meet their needs because there are not enough strong institutions that provide such services. Achieving sustainability means lowering transaction costs, offering services that are more useful to the clients, and finding new ways to provide banking services to the poor. It shows that access and efficient provision of microcredit can enable the poor to smooth their consumption, Better manage their risks better, gradually build their assets, develop their micro enterprises, enhance their income earning capacity and enjoy an improved quality of life. Micro finance services can also contribute to the improvement of resource allocation, promotion of markets, and adoption of better technology; thus, micro finance helps to promote economic growth and development.

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